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Primary Teachers' Experiences of Professional Development in Science by Distance Learning

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In 2007, the revised New Zealand Curriculum was introduced requiring New Zealand Primary schools to compulsorily teach Science (the Nature of Science strand) up to Year 10 (Ministry of Education, 2007). In spite of this, a number of international tests such as the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) indicate that New Zealand schools are not meeting this requirement. Compared with previous test reports, students still do not perform as well as students from other countries (Martin, Mallis, Foy, & Stanko, 2012). The Education Review Office (ERO) Chief Review Officer highlighted in the 2010 Science in The New Zealand Curriculum report that there was a lack of teacher confidence and capability in teaching science, and that there were limited opportunities for high quality professional development in science.

The New Zealand government considers that Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) subjects are linked to the future economic benefit of the nation (Ministry of Business, Innovation and Employment, 2014a). In 2014 the Minister of Education announced funds in the region of a half billion dollars to go towards "raising teaching quality to raise student achievement" (Ministry of Education, 2014a). Also of significance are the recently announced funds to support the objectives outlined in the joint Ministry of Education / Ministry of Business, Innovation and Employment 2014 Science in Society strategic plan and the "A Nation of Curious Minds" (Ministry of Business, Innovation and Employment, 2014b).

ISSUE

It could be argued that the investment by the government to "raise teaching quality" will need to have a lasting impact on the science activities children experience in school. Enabling teachers across the country to gain the knowledge, skills and confidence to teach authentic science should contribute to this lasting impact. The 2010 ERO Science report found that best practice in science teaching used authentic contexts and cross-curricula links. The Open Polytechnic developed a Primary Science Teaching programme as a response to these issues with a goal of improving the science knowledge, competence and confidence of primary teachers to teach science. It is delivered online to enable access for those working teachers who are geographically isolated.

The course was designed using the philosophy of making teachers look at the world and 'notice something worth noticing' as amateur scientists. This models the New Zealand Science curriculum where the Nature of Science (Ministry of Education, 2007) is the over-arching strand as the mechanism to support acquiring and testing new knowledge about the world.

METHODOLOGY

The authors carried out an analysis of over 200 samples of work from a total of 165 teachers from around New Zealand enrolled in Primary Science Teaching courses from 2012 to the end of 2014. Both qualitative and quantitative methods were used to explore the demographics of the cohort as well as beliefs and attitudes about science and science teaching.

To stimulate teachers' thoughts about the planning decisions they make in their science teaching, the Teaching Perspectives Inventory tool was used (Pratt & Collins, 2000). This online questionnaire provides an automated analysis with scores indicating how well beliefs about teaching and intentions for learning match the actions taken in the classroom. The five perspectives allow educators to identify the lens or teaching style they tend to use the most when manifesting their intentions for learning. The five perspectives are Transmission, Apprenticeship, Developmental, Nurturing, and Social Reform. The results of the Teaching Perspectives Inventory online tool provided further data for analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Statistics indicates the New Zealand Primary teaching workforce is typically female and over 40 years of age (Barback, 2013; Ministry of Education, 2012). This is mirrored in the enrolment data of teachers enrolled in the Primary Science Teaching (Table 1).

TABLE 1: Age and Ethnicity demographics of 165 teachers enrolled in the Graduate Certificate of Primary Science Teaching (Curriculum) from 2012 to 2014

- **Male:** 17%
 - **Female:** 83%
 - **NZ European:** 85%
 - **Maori:** 7%
 - **British/Irish:** 8%
 - **Under 30 years old:** 14%
 - **Over 40 years old:** 64%
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An analysis of 165 individuals indicated that the reasons teachers wanted to participate in professional development via online learning could be grouped into six categories:

- To gain confidence to do practical work,
- To gain content knowledge,
- School focus on raising profile of science,
- Learn about the Nature of Science strand,

- Learn about the "5 Capabilities" (Ministry of Education, 2014b), and
- Career progression.

The first compulsory course for these teachers in the curriculum certificate provided a number of opportunities for teachers to comment in forums prior to engaging in an authentic home-based science investigation. Prior to engaging with the course material, a number of themes were evident about existing beliefs and attitudes to science:

- Science only happens in a lab,
- Science is serious, can't be fun or enjoyable,
- Science is not creative,
- Science has nothing to do with numeracy or literacy, needs its own time slot,
- You need a lot of equipment, and
- All science follows a standard Scientific Method based on fair testing.

The teachers' expectations and beliefs appeared to be heavily influenced by their experiences of science at school. Students tended to adhere to a typical secondary school laboratory report template although the course guidance did not include this and had provided alternative formats for submissions.

At the start of the first compulsory course comments tended to align with the following themes:

- Children can't understand science concepts,
- Children can't do research,
- Children need to know content first,
- Anything children discover or notice has been seen before,
- Children cannot contribute anything meaningful to science,
- Children find science hard, and
- Science is for older children.

The extended period of time to do a real-world authentic investigation of genuine interest was for many a revelation about what science actually is and how science teaching could be done effectively.

Teacher A: I think the facts and the doing go together, especially for kids at school. This course is a blessing because I'm now getting to do the practical stuff and see the link between the two. Some 20 odd years later though!

Teacher B: This course has already opened up my eyes to thinking about what is important in science; my practice is already changing!

The extended length of time, the practical nature of the tasks, the ability to participate online from any geographical location, and the support of the tutor/mentor, appear to be the key features that increased the likelihood that new skills and attitudes were being retained and applied in the workplace. Evidence that attitudes and beliefs were being challenged was evident in the online forums as teachers shared their findings and talked

about the impact their learning would in changing classroom practice. Comments tended to align with the following examples:

- Science is just noticing something in particular that is worth noticing,
- Research is more than reading books or going online,
- You can't do science without counting, measuring or noticing proportions; maths is the language of science,
- There is so much happening in the world!,
- Fair tests are just one of the ways scientists investigate, and
- Time; I rush my students as I am busy ticking boxes.

With a new understanding of what it means to think and work scientifically, teachers started engaging with the content material to increase and challenge their knowledge. In pre-tests at the start of a five week block of work, teachers demonstrated relatively higher levels of prior knowledge of biology when compared with their prior knowledge of other science disciplines (physics, chemistry and earth science/astronomy). Teachers gained the most knowledge in the chemistry and physics courses during the five week period, but still scored lower in the summative task compared to biology and Earth science.

There is anecdotal evidence that Primary teachers feel the least confident about physics and Earth science/astronomy, and as a consequence these science topics are less likely to be taught in a school that does teach science. Our findings support this observation however comments in forums and messages to the tutor indicate that after completing the chemistry and physics courses, most teachers felt more confident to teach these less familiar concepts as they felt they could learn with their pupils. Gaining some content knowledge had also imparted a new confidence to teach.

Teacher C: I need a range of different activities based on the same context to enable my children to practice their new skills and consolidate their new knowledge in a variety of ways.

Once teachers have gained content knowledge and practical skills in the first four courses, the last courses requires teachers to demonstrate effective science teaching in their classrooms by carrying out a teaching action research project. The teachers that gained the most from this course engaged with the Teaching Perspectives Inventory tool more than once and reflected on what each of the perspectives meant in their context with their students. An analysis of scores and perspectives indicated no one perspective was the 'right' way to teach; each lens or style has advantages at different points of learning as well as being dependent on the beliefs, attitudes and intentions of the teacher.

Teacher D: Knowing one's teaching perspective and what our strengths are is important as they can influence the way we teach.

Teacher E: As a result of the TPI inventory it was highlighted for me that I have certain strengths and perspectives and this can influence how I approach my teaching; yet these perspectives and viewpoints may not always be best for my students.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

If subjects such as Science and Mathematics are priority subjects, professional development for teachers can be an issue, due to geographical isolation and obtaining time away from the classroom. Traditional professional development opportunities in Science are based on either 'bringing in an expert' or attending one day seminars or workshops. Neither option permits teachers to be supported to ask questions and trial new ideas about their Science teaching over a prolonged period.

The concept of an 'expert' teacher implies that there is one particular way to teach which is challenged by the results of this analysis. We have seen that in-service teachers were able to build up their own expertise and confidence to lead authentic practical science activities and become experts themselves. Rather than a 'one size fits all' approach, by participating in an online professional development opportunity different solutions appropriate to the culture of the school and the wider community were evident.

In summary, this model of distance learning for the professional development for working teachers is effective, and may be applied to other curriculum areas where geographical isolation or class release time may be an issue.

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